

FEATURES OF PRACTICAL PHYSICAL TRAINING OF ADOLESCENT STUDENTS

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Abstract.

This article contains the knowledge and skills of adolescent students and knowledge of physical culture, specific methods of practical physical training of adolescent students embodied.

Key words.

practical physical training, movement activity, movement training, movement skills, development, general physical training, special physical training.

In the teaching process, the terms "movement activity", "movement training", "movement skills", "movement skills", "theoretical knowledge", "ability to do", "education", "development" and so on are used and fulfills the purpose of providing physical information as mentioned above. By practicing physical training, playing sports or active games, we can save the energy that the body consumes by creating freedom and flexibility in our natural, not artificial, "good mood" movement. Such activity is considered as a training effect of physical exercise as a physiological condition, and biologically active substances created in the blood through this effect are slowly squeezed out of the blood composition of pathological agents caused by taking alcohol and drugs in the blood, according to sports physiology proved.

The main means of establishing practical physical training of the perfect generation is aimed at expressing the development and direction of physical education and sports in our country.

Training (if the load is in moderation) the exerciser feels relief and observes similar situations as if he has become physically stronger is proof of the above. All this is related to the level of our health that should be achieved during the life process, and the knowledge we have acquired to know how to catch it at the right level.

In the study of the physical fitness of teenage students in order to study and achieve high results in higher education institutions, it was found that 50.0% of teenage students who are able to meet the requirements of the test according to the standards of the horizontal bar "students were evaluated satisfactorily, which indicates that most of the young people have average physical fitness.

Studies conducted during the academic year show that the dynamics of the studied problem is also important. The traditional self-formation formed in the system of physical education can reveal its effective aspects.

The statistical materials obtained during the research show that the general possibilities of practical physical training of young people are very high.

At the end of the academic year, we witnessed that only a small part of the teenage students did not pay enough attention to the planned physical education activities between classes.

In a study of practical physical fitness of teenage students, the level of pedagogical assessment was good and excellent, only 45.8%. According to the standards of general physical fitness, 34.2% were good and excellent. The low level of training in practical physical training was 20%.

In fact, it is necessary to increase year by year the indicators of general and practical physical training for young people studying in higher education institutions and secondary education system.

However, the results of the conducted control show that students of adolescent age cannot fulfill the norms if special physical training is not organized.

well-rounded and healthy generation is considered one of the most urgent problems of every country. The future of every country, its development and prosperity will grow, It plays a direct role in where and how the upbringing of the new generation is carried out, how the personality of the students of the teenage age is formed. In our country, the pedagogical process of physical education is carried out through the stages of higher and secondary special vocational education based on the state program.

The solution of any problems faced by the system of higher and secondary special vocational education is determined by determining the quality of continuous physical education and the actual content of their didactic base. It is possible to achieve the quality level of physical fitness of teenage students through the use of physical education tools. But their sequence and order of use must be strictly suitable for each age group.

Taking into account the expediency of the current standardization of physical education, knowledge of physical culture requires the regulation of initial development, and teachers are required to look for new opportunities in the process of creative activity.

The development of society, nation, nation is measured in its socio-educational development, and the level of this development is called the members of the society, the people, which depends on the level of physical fitness of the human person.

Preparation is absent in mental, moral, spiritual and other types of education. But the main one of them is the individual's physical fitness, it has its place.

Is a very common term, its definition is not well defined in the specialized literature. In all the literature of physical education, theoretical and practical sections on its indicators and methods of their development are given, and we tried to explain its pure definition. In terms of individual, personality, physical maturity of students of adolescent age, physical fitness of young people, based on their physical development, we interpreted it as "the level of work ability achieved in the formation of vital and practical skills and k skills that embody the effectiveness of purposeful activity".

Is closer to the definitions given in the L.T.Matveev Institute of Physical Education for students of the adolescent age, and we consider it a detailed definition of the level of work ability achieved.

In simpler terms, "The ability to effectively perform life-practical activities, which occurs from the strength, endurance, agility, quickness, mobility and elasticity of the muscles of the human body, can be called physical fitness."

Because, if the qualities we have listed can be shown well, if they can be strong, durable, agile, fast, if they can show these qualities in their own way, then it is right to be called "Polvan" and "Bohodir" in Uzbek must be.

Therefore, it is called "the level of movement qualities of the human body, indicators of physical fitness".

Taking into account the appropriate age for the formation of the foundation of the individual, the physical maturity of the individual organism, we made their physical fitness the object of study. Because movement qualities such as strength, speed, endurance, agility, muscle elasticity are average, their influence on the effectiveness of various vital and practical activities until old age has been reflected in many literary and scientific studies.

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